

A Kernel average misorientation evaluation of surface alterations caused by angled droplet impingements

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Abstract: The droplet impact angle on the solid surface plays a crucial role in the erosion development, which is critical in structural applications. In the present study, a pulsating water jet with a frequency of 40 kHz generated droplets impacting surface of steel. The number of droplet impingements ranged from 20,000 to 400,000 (0.5 to 10 s). The impact angle was 90°, 75°, 60°, 45°. The exposure longer than 3 s caused material removal. The exposure 3 s or less caused surface roughening. The SEM observation of the roughened surface was supplemented by the roughness, and the kernel average misorientation analysis. Proposed segmentation delineates the non-uniformity of erosion and outlines the damage contours, which helps predict location of material removal onset.

Keywords: droplet impingement, impact angle, erosion, electron microscopy

Highlights:

- Erosion damage segmentation helps predicts and quantify configuration of erosion stages.
- Erosion stages vary within a single cross-section due to the droplet's uneven velocity fields.
- The physical structure and velocity characteristics of water droplets significantly influence erosion.
- Erosion at 60° and 75° shows similar erosion effects.
- Erosion caused by impact at 45° angle show significant drop compared to 75°, and 60°.

1. Introduction

The study of erosion mechanisms, particularly concerning the impact angles of droplets, has gained significant attention due to its critical implications in various engineering applications [1,2]. Most studies investigate the action of drops in the perpendicular direction, where the most significant impact pressure is assumed. The phenomenon known as impact pressure [1] is directly proportional to the density of the impacting liquid, the speed of the drop, and the speed of the acoustic wave, which is created at the contact periphery due to the impact of the droplet on a solid surface. The erosion depends on parameters such as impact velocity [3], impact frequency [4], the size of the impacting droplet, and the impact angle [5][6]. Although the perpendicular impact of the droplets to the target surface is found to be most significant in terms of erosion damage [6][7], studying water droplet impingement on tilted solid surfaces is also crucial due to applications involving non-perpendicular impacts in contexts such as rain erosion of wind turbine blades [8,9] and the performance of steam turbine blades [10,11]. Surfaces of structural parts in applications experience various impact angles, influencing erosion patterns and material degradation differently. By investigating droplet behavior on tilted surfaces, more accurate predictive models and effective mitigation strategies can be developed, ultimately enhancing the durability and performance of critical components in various industries. Study [12] contributes to the broader understanding of droplet impact dynamics, suggesting that a multifaceted approach is necessary to comprehend fully the multiple outcomes of droplet-surface interactions [13]. The research in [14] offers valuable insights for practical applications in preventing ice accretion on hydrophobic textured surfaces. The investigation focuses on four levels of the droplet-

to-substrate attack angle from 90° to 45°, i.e., the tilt angle of the substrate relative to the horizontal axis varied from 0° to 45°. The study aims to understand how surface texture influences droplet spreading by applying parallel-directed scratches using a grinding machine.

Most research papers, such as [5] and [12] primarily focus on the perpendicular impact of water jets with solid surfaces, leaving a gap in knowledge regarding the erosion evolution of surfaces due to droplets impacting at an angle. This deficiency is particularly evident in complex surfaces, where non-perpendicular impacts are natural. This study aims to bridge this gap by systematically investigating the effects of different impact angles on erosion using austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L as the target material. By employing a pulsating water jet (PWJ) to generate droplets with varying numbers of impingements (erosion time) and angular deviations, this research provides an understanding of how impact angles influence erosion patterns on the contact periphery of the solid surface. Two ranges of exposure time ($t = 0.5 - 3$ s and $t = 4 - 10$ s) were selected based on erosion analysis, and a combination of various evaluation techniques was adopted for individual segments of erosion pits. The segmentation of the impacted area and the correlation of roughness development with kernel average misorientation analysis provided a detailed description of erosion mechanisms across created erosion craters at initial stages of wear created under low exposure time. Understanding insights is essential for creating predictive models and engineering strategies to reduce the negative impact of erosion in structural applications.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Experimental material

Austenitic stainless steel AISI 316L, commonly used in various applications, was selected for this experiment. The material was delivered as a plate of thickness approximately 20 mm in hot rolled conditions. The yield strength of the material was 322 MPa, and the hardness was 184 ± 10 HV0.2. The steel consists mainly of austenite (face-centered cubic lattice) and a small percentage of ferritic bands (body-centered cubic lattice). Except for the highly homogenous microstructure with an area-weighted equivalent circle diameter grain size of approximately 20 μm , it possesses corrosion resistance to the humid tap water environment, which enhances the repeatability and reliability of the experiment during the processing by the PWJ technology. The chemical composition of AISI 316L in wt. % is as follows: Cr 16.63, Ni 10.00, Mo 2.04, Mn 1.26, Si 0.38, C 0.02, N 0.04, P 0.032, S 0.001, Fe rest [15]. Rectangular samples of dimensions 25x20x150 mm were cut from the plate, and the surface under investigation was mechanically and electrolytically polished before PWJ treatment with variable impact angle.

2.2. Water jet treatment

The impact of water droplets was achieved using an ultrasonic pulsating water jet developed at the Institute of Geonics of the Czech Academy of Sciences [16,17]. High-frequency pulses are produced at the tip of the sonotrode, which oscillates within an acoustic chamber. Mechanical oscillations are created by the inverse piezoelectric effect, converting the electrodynamic signal from the acoustic generator. This process involves a set of piezoelectric transducers attached to the top of the sonotrode. Pressure fluctuations transform into velocity fluctuations after passing through the nozzle exit [18]. It leads to the gradual formation of discrete water droplet clusters [19]. The initial hydraulic parameters set for the experiment were as follows: supply pressure $p = 50$ MPa generated by Hammelman HDP 235 pump and circular nozzle with diameter $d = 0.6$ mm. Hydraulic conditions generated a water flow rate of $Q = 4.83$ l/min with a velocity of $v_w = 284.89$ m/s. This jet velocity can be assumed to be equal to impact velocity if the atmospheric drag is neglected. Optimal technological parameters such

as acoustic chamber length l_c and standoff distance z were set based on selected hydraulic parameters to maximize the erosion potential of water droplets (see *Table 1*). Tuning of the l_c was performed according to [20] and for optimization of the z , the stair trajectory technique was employed to avoid possible Doppler effect contribution[21].

Table 1 Experimental parameters

Hydraulic conditions					Technological parameters		Experimental variations		
Supply pressure p (MPa)	Nozzle diameter d (mm)	Impact velocity v_w (m/s)	Flow rate Q (l/min)	Frequency f_s (kHz)	Acoustic chamber length l_c (mm)	Standoff distance z (mm)	Exposure time t (s)	Impact angle α (°)	Rep (-)
50	0.6	284.89	4.83	40	10	62	0.5; 0.67; 0.75; 1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10	90; 75; 60; 45	3x

The samples were fixed in a clamping device with an adjustable inclination to facilitate the determination of the influence of the impact angle on the development of erosion. The impact angle α is defined as the angle between the trajectory of the impinging water droplets and the inclined plane of the target material surface, similarly as described in [22]. The impact angle can also be defined as the attack angle [23]. The impact angle α during the PWJ exposure was changed by tilting to four levels of surface inclination, i.e., $\alpha = 45, 60, 75,$ and 90° , as shown in *Figure 1*. The goal was to evaluate erosion development based on the combination of impact angle and the number of water impacts related to the exposure time ($t = 0.5; 0.67; 0.75; 1; 2; 3; 4; 5; 6; 7; 8; 9; 10$ s). It allowed observation of erosion development from the erosion incubation stage up to material removal. Each experimental run was repeated three times to ensure statistical significance.

Figure 1 Experimental setup showing a schematic of hydraulic assembly and overview of experimental variations

2.3. Profile measurement

The surface damaged by repeated water impingement was assessed by a non-contact approach using an InfiniteFocus G5 (Bruker, Alicona) optical 3D measurement system. The measurement is based on focus variation combined with vertical scanning. The surface data were evaluated by using MountainSPIP software. Quantitative analysis of PWJ erosion was divided into two parts concerning time exposure ranges resulting in 1) erosion surface roughening (0.5 – 3s) and 2) erosion material removal (i.e., 4 – 10s). The second part of the experimental data was evaluated regarding erosion depth and removed volume. It was evaluated based on the area of 2x2 mm covering the entire crater and adjacent surroundings. Three erosion craters created by the same hydraulic conditions (labeled 1st, 2nd, and 3rd run) were analyzed, and the maximum and average values of depth and volume were determined. The first part of experimental data concerning the exposed surface, without significant material removal, was evaluated using parameter **Pt**, i.e., the total height of the primary profile according to ISO 21920-2 [24]. Previous research [25] showed that the roughness distribution on the surface exposed to stationary water impacts induced by PWJ is highly inhomogeneous. Therefore, we adopted the measuring strategy as shown in *Figure 2*. The **Pt** was evaluated along several lines with a length of 500 μm . The measurement lines were aligned to be parallel, and the shift between them was set to be 150 μm to cover the whole affected area. Measurements from each run were labeled A, B, and C for the first, second, and third runs, respectively. The measurement position was set to cover areas from insignificant erosion up to the most damaged area. Ten lines were evaluated for each run and the averaged value of the total height of the profile $Pt_{average}$ was calculated as follows:

$$Pt_{average} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{10} Pt(A)_i + \sum_{i=1}^{10} Pt(B)_i + \sum_{i=1}^{10} Pt(C)_i}{30} \quad (1)$$

$$Pt_{max} = \frac{Pt(A)_{max} + Pt(B)_{max} + Pt(C)_{max}}{3} \quad (2)$$

The Pt_{iA} , Pt_{iB} , and Pt_{iC} are i^{th} total height of the profile from the crater in 1st, 2nd, and 3rd runs, respectively. The Pt_{max} is then the highest **Pt** value measured across all three measured craters (eq. 2).

Figure 2 Schematic of Pt measurement strategy for craters treated with an exposure time of 3 s and less

2.4. SEM and EBSD observations

Observation of erosion marks created on polished surfaces by application of PWJ under variable impact angle was performed using the scanning electron microscope (SEM) Tescan Lyra3 XMU FEG/SEMxFIB (Tescan, Czech Republic) equipped with EBSD detector Symmetry, equipped with AZtec Crystal evaluation software (Oxford Instruments, United Kingdom). EBSD analysis provided data concerning the grain size and the crystallographic orientation but also enabled evaluation of the deformation of the surface grains using Kernel Average Misorientation (KAM) analysis. The EBSD map was set to be with the size of 2200 x 200 μm . The width of the map covered the whole width of the erosion crater; nevertheless, the height map was limited due to the length of time needed to reach the reasonable measurement time. The step size was set to 0.5 μm for sufficient scanning sensitivity.

Data obtained by KAM analysis was further processed in the open-source MTEX v5.7.0 [26] toolbox for MATLAB because it contains a half-quadratic filter [27], a noise-reducing filter explicitly designed for EBSD data. The combination of MTEX with MATLAB also provided functions to post-process EBSD maps with greater complexity than official software. The KAM analysis can be correlated with the dislocation density [28] and is, therefore, a great candidate for evaluating the plastic deformation caused by repeated droplet impacts. KAM analysis is based on comparing the crystal orientation of the scanned point (pixel) with the orientations of adjacent pixels. The average orientation difference between the pixels is the local value of the KAM angle. The KAM map is then assessed by calculating the local KAM values for all the pixels in the EBSD map. The first order of neighbors was used to evaluate KAM° in this study.

3. Results

The first assessment of the topography of all erosion areas created by PWJ acting on a flat surface of stainless steel samples under four levels of impact angle α under the whole range of exposure times of PWJ was performed qualitatively using scanning electron microscopy (SEM). The effect of angle impingement was further evaluated differently based on the two ranges of exposure time. The boundary condition between two exposure time ranges has been selected as 3 s based on Pt measurement and its standard deviation, which roughly equates to 120,000 impacts.

The range related to higher values of time exposure (4 - 10 s) exhibiting significant roughness and material removal was analyzed quantitatively by measurement of erosion depth and volume, while short exposure times (0.5 - 3 s), i.e., initial stages of erosion before macroscopic material removal were evaluated employing a profile parameter Pt and combined with KAM analysis derived from EBSD data.

3.1. SEM observations

SEM micrographs of erosion obtained by PWJ treatment under four incident angles for five exposure times selected approximately exponentially from the whole experimental range of exposure times are shown in *Figure 3*, *Figure 4*, and *Figure 5*

Figure 3 shows the overview pictures of the impacted sites at lower magnification (50 x). The SEM observation is extremely sensitive for setting brightness and contrast, especially in incubation stages of erosion, so it is necessary to be aware of it, otherwise it can lead to misinterpretation of results. This disadvantage can be overcome by supplementary measurement of roughness parameters and KAM analysis (see results below). The SEM observation shows that maximum erosion was reached using $\alpha = 90^\circ$. A certain anomaly occurred in the case of $\alpha = 60^\circ$ at exposure time 5 s, which exhibits material removal compared to $\alpha = 75^\circ$ for the same time exposure, which provides only a rough surface. In all cases of the impact angles, it is also possible to observe the localization of roughening

of the surface at small exposure times (2 s), i.e., inhomogeneous roughness over the whole erosion pit area, which is then followed by localization of material removal under higher exposure times and creation of crescent shape of erosion valley.

Figure 3 SEM overview shows the erosion evolution for five selected exposure times (print mag. 50x).

The more detailed SEM micrographs of the central eroded area for the same selected erosion exposure times are presented in Figure 4. At magnification of 500x, it is possible to see the first signs of plastic deformation on the surface in case of short exposures such as 0.5 s. This deformation is observed in the form of exposed grain boundaries. Surface steps caused by either twins or grain boundaries can be observed in preferably oriented grains. They were observed in all impact angles at all exposure times until the material removal started. Material removal begins in the form of microscopic cavities. It occurred first in the case of exposure of 2 s at $\alpha = 90^\circ$. Similar processes with slightly elongated incubation are documented after 5 s exposure at $\alpha = 75^\circ$, 60° and 45° . Exposure to PWJ for 5 s at $\alpha = 90^\circ$ nevertheless results in the formation of a macroscopic erosion crater. To create a macroscopic crater under lower impact angles of the PWJ treatment, exposure longer than 5 s is necessary, as seen in the case of 10 s of exposure in Figure 4. At the magnification of 500x, typical signs of significant erosion damage are visible at the bottom of the erosion crater, including small micro-voids and cavities, as well as a network of cracks connecting these cavities (see Figure 4, 5 s exposure under $\alpha = 90^\circ$ or 10 s exposure under all four levels of α).

Figure 4 SEM detail of central eroded area for selected erosion exposure times (print mag. 500x).

In Figure 5, the highest magnification micrographs (5000x) describe a local material response to droplet impingement based on erosion exposure time and impact angle. Details show specific features related to water jetting and different levels of created erosion from the incubation stage up to material removal.

The short time exposures (see 0.5 s; 1 s and 2 s in Figure 5) exhibited, in the case of all impact angles, the presence of surface steps typical for plastic deformation due to the repetitive action of water droplets. Intricate formations of these surface steps are visible. In some cases, surface steps end in contact with adjacent surface steps, twin, or grain boundaries. In some cases (see $\alpha = 45^\circ$, 1 s), the surface steps sharply change orientation upon interaction with perpendicular surface steps. Similarly, as in the case of smaller magnification micrographs, also here in Figure 5, the anomaly for erosion under $\alpha = 60^\circ$ is evident, where at 2 s of exposure, surface damage exhibiting multiple surface steps in a quite complex manner with sharp breaks reaches a significantly higher erosion level than exposure under $\alpha = 75^\circ$ showing only surface deformation consisting of three parallel surface steps. The bottom of the erosion kerf for higher exposure (5 s) is characterized by typical signs such as micro-cavities in case of 90° impingement.

On the other hand, lesser angles showcase localized damage, such as a microcavity at angle 75°, first signs of material removal at surface steps in case of angle 60°, or removed material adherent to surface steps at 45°. The high exposure time (10 s) results in macroscopic material removal, leading to the creation of erosion kerf. The bottom of these kerfs shows a very rough fractured surface with several micro-cavities and secondary cracks usually propagating from these cavities. Surroundings of these cavities exhibit the presence of relatively flat areas.

Figure 5 SEM detail showing local material response to droplet impingement based on erosion exposure time (print mag. 5000x).

3.2. Profile measurement

As was described in *Chapter 2.3.*, the quantitative analysis of PWJ erosion was divided into two parts concerning time exposure ranges resulting in 1) erosion surface roughening for exposure to PWJ for 0.5 s up to 3 s, or 2) erosion material removal, related to the application of PWJ for 4 s and longer. Exposure times longer than 4 s are responsible for the creation of deep erosion craters with significant material removal. The results of measurement are presented in terms of depth of erosion and removed volume in *Figure 6*.

Figure 6 a shows the dependencies of average erosion depth generated by the application of PWJ with variable exposure time and four levels of impact angle. Both average and maximum depth reached the highest values in the case of treatment under $\alpha = 90^\circ$. Dependencies were increasing with a slight anomaly observable at the exposure time of approximately 6 s for $\alpha = 75^\circ$.

The effect of impact angle and exposure time was also evaluated as volume removed during erosion (see *Figure 6 b*). Eroded volume values increased with the exposure time and reached the highest values when PWJ was applied under $\alpha = 90^\circ$. Removed volume exhibits a significant distance between data curves/dependencies for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and other impact angles. Another interesting observation was that data from eroded volume evaluation confirmed certain anomalies for $\alpha = 60^\circ$, similarly as observed qualitatively from SEM analysis. As is visible from *Figure 6*, for exposure time in the interval between 9 and 10 s, the volume removed by erosion was higher for $\alpha = 60^\circ$ than for $\alpha = 75^\circ$.

Figure 6 Average a) depth and b) volume removed achieved with ranging exposure time based on the impact angle.

Since the above-mentioned depth and volume analysis are not sensitive enough in the case of a very short exposure time, i.e., below 4 s, another parameter was adopted to describe the effect of impact angle on erosion resistance against periodical impingement by water droplets. According to Chapter 2.3. the total height of the primary profile P_t was used.

Plots in Figure 7 show the evaluation of surface topography at an incubation erosion stage of PWJ treatment for all four levels of impact angle, i.e., $\alpha = 90^\circ$, 75° , 60° , and 45° , respectively.

Results concerning the average and maximum values of profile parameter P_t show that the maximum erosive effect can be observed in the case of treatment under an impact angle of 90° . The extremely high standard deviation observed at $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and 3 s exposure is caused by significant inhomogeneity of erosion across the measured area and further damage localization, as already seen in micrographs in Figure 3.

Figure 7 Average and maximum profile parameter P_t achieved with ranging exposure time based on the impact angle

Due to the significant difference between the P_t parameter achieved for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ and other applied impact angles, it is difficult to assess the effect of lower angles. Therefore, the dependencies were presented again in Figure 8, where data for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ were omitted. Interestingly, again, at $\alpha = 60^\circ$, a higher erosive effect was reached than in the case of $\alpha = 75^\circ$ for exposure time higher than approximately 1.5 s. However, considering standard deviations, the effect of impingement under these

two impact angles is quite close. The roughening caused by impact at $\alpha = 45^\circ$ is slightly smaller considering the average Pt and significantly smaller in the case of the maximum Pt measured.

Figure 8 Average and maximum profile parameter P_t achieved for exposure time between 0.75 and 3 s based on the impact angle omitting data for 90° impact angle.

3.3. EBSD measurement

Selected results of EBSD analysis performed on 316L samples treated by PWJ for variable exposure time and four values of impact angle can be seen in Figure 9, Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12 in the form of KAM maps evaluated from EBSD data across the whole width of the erosion crater (area of $2200 \times 200 \mu\text{m}$) for three selected levels of exposure time (0.5, 1 and 2 s) and an impact angle of 90° , 75° , 60° and 45° , respectively. All observed features were related to the x position.

The misorientation angle is expressed in each scanned point by color according to the attached colormap. It should be noted that in all pictures, the black color corresponds to places with zero solution, i.e., either the local deformation of grain boundaries or areas was too severe or the roughness of the surface was too high for the EBSD method to evaluate crystallographic data. The blue color corresponds to a local misorientation angle reaching a value of about 1.5° , and blue lines inside of grains suggest the formation of low-angle boundaries (LABs).

Figure 9 shows KAM maps for $\alpha = 90^\circ$. The creation of LABs inside the grains is apparent, with the highest concentration of blue areas close to the x position at about $1400 \mu\text{m}$ for the exposure time of 0.5 s. At the same x position, there is also a significant increase in the concentration of zero solutions (black color). A similar trend can be observed in the case of all selected exposure times. The longer the exposure time, the higher the rate of zero solutions; moreover, the small areas with zero solutions appear in more places along the scanned area. The localization of zero solutions around the x position of $1600 \mu\text{m}$ is distinctly apparent in the case of 2 s of exposure to PWJ. The adjacent area ($x = 600\text{--}1200 \mu\text{m}$) shows a very high concentration of LABs.

Figure 9 EBSD strip measurement across surfaces subjected to droplet impingement at 90° for varying time exposure

Figure 10 shows KAM maps for $\alpha = 75^\circ$. The exposure of 0.5 s leads to a significantly wider area with high LABs concentration (compared to $\alpha = 90^\circ$ in Figure 10); nevertheless, the amount of zero solutions is considerably lower. An increase in exposure time to 1 s led to a higher concentration of LABs from $x = 400$ to $1600 \mu\text{m}$. Furthermore, between $x = 1200 \mu\text{m}$ and $1700 \mu\text{m}$, there is a visible increase in zero solutions. This fact again points to the localization of erosion. The exposure time of 2 s led to an increase in zero solutions from $x = 600 \mu\text{m}$ to $1600 \mu\text{m}$. In contrast to 2 s exposure under $\alpha = 90^\circ$, the area of the zero solutions is less localized and more spread at $\alpha = 75^\circ$. It also corresponds to the result of the Pt parameter, where the area containing zero solutions is, according to Pt values, more eroded in the case of treatment with PWJ by 2 s under $\alpha = 90^\circ$. The zero solutions are less localized and spread around most of the crater at $\alpha = 75^\circ$.

Figure 10 EBSD strip measurement across surfaces subjected to droplet impingement at 75° for varying time exposure

Figure 11 shows KAM maps for $\alpha = 60^\circ$. The trend is similar to $\alpha = 75^\circ$, where the density of LABs is more homogeneously distributed across the erosion crater width, contrary to the highly localized situation at $\alpha = 90^\circ$. Exposure of 0.5 s leaves a trace of increased LAB density from around $x = 400 \mu\text{m}$ to about $x = 1800 \mu\text{m}$ with occasional zero solutions at grain boundaries in the most intensely eroded area. The apparent density of LABs increases with increment of exposure to 1 s. KAM map for exposure

of 2 s shows the appearance of points with zero solutions on a significant part of the exposed surface from $x = 500 \mu\text{m}$ to $1700 \mu\text{m}$. It means that erosion is significantly more homogenous than in the case of $\alpha = 75^\circ$. It corresponds to the anomaly observed on SEM micrographs as well as the anomaly depicted by a higher level of Pt parameter for $\alpha = 60^\circ$ over the value for $\alpha = 75^\circ$ in the exposure time interval between 1.5 and 3 s (see *Figure 11*).

Figure 11 EBSD strip measurement across surfaces subjected to droplet impingement at 60° for varying time exposure

Figure 12 shows KAM maps for $\alpha = 45^\circ$. The density of LABs is the lowest from all impact angles under investigation; nevertheless, the trend is the same, and the density of LABs increases with increasing exposure time. At an exposure time of 2 s, zero solutions increased from $x = 600 \mu\text{m}$ to $1400 \mu\text{m}$. However, the apparent density of zero solutions is smaller, and visible zero solutions seem to follow grain boundaries in most cases.

Figure 12 EBSD strip measurement across surfaces subjected to droplet impingement at 45° for varying time exposure

Data from KAM analysis was also processed into graphs (see *Figure 13*), where KAM angles and zero solutions were analyzed in dependence on short exposure times for all impact angles. The averaged values of KAM angles are present in *Figure 13 a*. Note: Due to the relatively high portion of zero solutions in the case of exposure 2 s, the value for an impact angle of 60° is severely underestimated.

Figure 13 b shows a dependency of zero solutions on increasing exposure time, where the amount of zero solutions at 0.5 s exposure creates an area between 10 % and 12% of the analyzed surface for all impact angles. The highest percentage of zero solutions was evaluated in the case of an impact angle of 60° at the exposure of 2s, where it reached 45 % of the observed area. It is striking compared to an impact angle of 90° at the exposure of 2 s, where it reached only 28 % of the measured area. The high localization of erosion caused by an angle of 90° is the probable reason, as the zero solutions are concentrated at a smaller area, compared to a 60° angle where they cover the marginal part of the impacted surface. Nevertheless, the high level of zero solutions at an exposure time of 2 s and their localization conceding with the highest roughness should be considered when interpreting the average KAM angle at higher exposure times.

Figure 13 Plots of average KAM angle and zero solutions evaluated across the entire map in dependence on low exposure time.

3.4. Spatial line evaluation

Figure 14 shows panoramic micrographs across the erosion crater width for all the impact angles for one selected exposure time of 2 s. The picture was created by connecting individual SEM figures.

Figure 14 Panorama from connected SEM micrographs showing the erosion progression spread across the exposed area for exposure time 2 s.

Close to the center of the pictures (Figure 14), there is always an area with localized erosion features. With increasing distance from this center, the exposed grain boundaries are present, which creates surface steps and leads to surface roughening. Surface steps along grain boundaries are visible at all impact angles. In some grains, there are visible arrays of surface steps. The surface steps appear more prominent in the case of 90° and 60° impact angles. The observed mechanisms of roughening in the center of incidence of water droplets are again the creation of surface steps at grain boundaries and inside of the grains followed by the beginning of material removal. In the case of lower angles, accumulation of damage along grain boundaries is apparent. With increasing impact angle, the appearance of surface cavities increases, located preferably close to grain boundaries, marking the onset of material removal. It is important to note that this surface topography, just before material removal, represents the limit for EBSD analysis because it produces such a high number of zero solutions.

Figure 15 shows the Pt of erosion craters in 1st run based on their position (see Figure 2). The 1 s exposure to $\alpha = 90^\circ$ caused a rise in Pt values from 2.1 μm at the erosion crater edge to about 4.7 μm in the most damaged area. With decreasing impact angle ($\alpha = 75^\circ$, 60°, and 45°), the value of the Pt parameter decreased (4.1 μm , 3.7 μm , and 2.8 μm , respectively) for the most damaged area.

The 2 s exposure at $\alpha = 90^\circ$ caused the rise of the Pt value (6.8 μm) significantly more than for lower angles (4.3 μm , 4.5 μm , and 2.8 μm for 75°, 60°, and 45°, respectively). In the graph, the localization of Pt increases in the case of 90° is obvious for the x position between 800 μm and 1200 μm . It is also apparent from the graph that roughness characterized by the Pt parameter is for $\alpha = 60^\circ$ in many places higher than for $\alpha = 75^\circ$. Moreover, curves for treatment under $\alpha = 60^\circ$ show relatively consistent roughness across most of the measured areas, while the dependence for $\alpha = 90^\circ$ exhibits a peak representing a localization of erosion.

A similar situation is in the case of 3 s; nevertheless, data points for exposure at $\alpha = 90^\circ$ are far ahead of all the lower angles, reaching Pt close to 40 μm . Localization is also very prominent in positions between 1000 and 14000 μm , as shown in the graph. Similarly to 1 s, exposure at $\alpha = 60^\circ$ shows approximately equivalent Pt values across most of the measured area. On the other hand, impacts at $\alpha = 75^\circ$ show some degree of damage localization.

Figure 15 Distribution of Pt along the erosion craters in 1st run for time exposure $t = 1, 2,$ and 3 s.

Figure 16 shows, similar to Figure 15, the variation of KAM angles across eroded areas. Each graph of the figure shows three levels of time exposure (0.5, 1, and 2 s) for the selected impact angle. The KAM of as-received material and its average has also been added. The average KAM value of the as-received surface is 0.288, showing the effect of material technological history (hot rolling). The green line shows the effect of 0.5 s of exposure to water impacts. This line is higher than the average of the as-received surface in all angles except 45° , where it overcomes as-received material only locally. Due to a low number of zero solutions, this line can be considered valid. However, in the case of 2 s exposure and partially also 1 s exposure, the high number of zero solutions causes, that the KAM values underestimate the level of surface deformation. In the case of 90° due to erosion localization, the higher value appears to be at the place adjacent to the most damaged area ($x = 500$) because there is

a lot of LABS measured (see Figure 10), whereas the area with the most significant erosion is full of zero solutions effectively lowering measured value.

Figure 16 Averaged KAM distribution across the erosion kerf with relevance to X coordinates location.

4. Discussion

4.1. Limits of the EBSD approach

It has been shown that the KAM calculated from the EBSD data is very dependent on the used step size [29,30]. Thus, the same step size (1 μm) is used for each EBSD map to ensure comparability.

Another critical parameter for the KAM is achievable angular resolution [31,32], which depends on the used EBSD detector and the quality of the Kikuchi patterns. The EBSD detector manufacturer (Oxford Instruments) claims a peak angular resolution of 0.05° . Most of LAB revealed by the KAM here are higher than 0.5° , which is high above the stated angular resolution limit. Furthermore, the Half Quadratic Filter [33] applied in this work has been shown to clear noise and preserve the LAB [25,31]. The EBSD signal originates from a near sub-surface region of the interaction volume between the electron beam and the material. Due to this, the method is sensitive to surface roughness and severely high dislocation density, both of which weaken the signal and can cause empty regions in the EBSD maps [34]. This knowledge indicates that the empty regions in the EBSD maps correspond to the most severely deformed areas, where the damaging effect of the droplet impact is strongest.

4.2. Spatially non-uniform erosion development

The following paragraph provides a comprehensive analysis of the non-uniformity of the development of erosion within a given time frame, attributing this phenomenon to an uneven velocity field distribution. The observations made during the experiment support this assumption, suggesting that technical factors and the physical structure of water droplets play significant roles [35]. Measurements and analyses reported in the results chapter show that erosion development within a given time frame may not be uniform (*Figure 2*). This spatial variation in erosion stages may result from an uneven velocity field distribution. This assumption appears reasonable, given that the phenomenon was consistently observed during multiple runs of the experiment, as also observed in [36] and [37]. Unconsidered technical factors, such as impact angles, might be responsible for the uneven velocity field distribution observed across the droplet cross-section. More importantly, a single surface cross-section impinged by consecutively repeating drops contains different erosion stages, from incubation to accumulation and attenuation occurring simultaneously. The cross-section could be better evaluated by dividing it into segments based on their erosion state. The segmentation of the eroded crater can be proposed based on optical micrographs, even in the case of the rotating disc type of device shown in [38]. The spatial segmentation into three regions was also used to study erosion kerfs created by hydrodynamic nozzles [39]. Analyzing the distribution of the spatially based erosion segments can be used to evaluate inconsistencies in inhomogeneous impact pressure distribution or divergence from ideal droplet geometry. It suggests that the erosion evolution process can also be considered from time and spatial points of view (*Table 2*).

Most types of devices employed to investigate water droplet erosion use artificially accelerated droplets, such as pulsed water jets [40], or droplets colliding with an object moving at high speeds, such as whirling-arm testers [41,42]. It creates different impact conditions than the impact of a drop naturally accelerating in a gravitational field. This is because the impact velocity affects the value of C , the speed of the acoustic wave in the drop. In [43,44], it was analytically and numerically characterized that for an impact velocity of 500 m/s, the speed of the compression wave during the initial phase of impingement was found to be approximately 2600–3000 m/s. It is significantly higher than the speed of sound in water under ambient conditions where $C = 1430$ m/s [45]. However, the mechanism of droplet acceleration or creation may lead to an unevenly distributed velocity field or atypical droplet geometry, as seen in the case of ultrasonically induced pulsating water jet [46].

Findings contradict the currently accepted theory based on the hypothesis of a water droplet acting as a spherical object represented in two-dimensional Euclidean space [9,47]. This intuitive model was designed to closely simulate the interaction between the sample and flowing water, aiming to approximate erosion development along the impact line in high-speed rotating wheels [9,48]. The model helped to understand both the basic and extended features of the erosion behavior of water droplets [49]. The model introduced various models of the impact pressure relationship [50] and

elucidated the effects of the subsequent erosion factor—lateral jetting [44]. However, non-uniform areas were observed along the contact line as well. This irregularity could be linked to the uneven distribution of mechanical properties since polycrystalline materials contain grains with different crystallographic orientations relative to the impact load. Another possible cause might be the inconsistencies in water velocity distribution, resulting in an inhomogeneous impact pressure distribution or deviation from the considered spherical droplet geometry.

Previous studies have observed comparable features where successive droplets were directed at a single location [25]. This specific location exhibited erosion characterized by temporal variation within the erosion horizon, defined as the radius of action of water droplets. Therefore, the uneven distribution may be attributed to the varying velocity vector distributions of water droplets within the cross-section, which directly influence the magnitude of the impact pressure at specific local segments (*Figure 17*). In this case, the segmentation only in one cross-sectional direction consists of finding the maximum value of the parameter (in this case, Pt). Then, the parameter is measured in equidistant spacings. Each value then can be expressed as a percentage of the maximum value. Segmentation of spatial erosion area is based on artificial relativistic boundaries (i.e., 40 % and 20 %) compared to the maximal measured parameter value to be usable for all erosion stages.

Figure 17 A new hierarchy of erosion activity from the perspective of the spatial classification of erosion segment distribution using the total height of profile parameter suggestion depicting incubation erosion stage and suggestion of modification for terminal erosion stage.

Figure 17 shows the distribution of segments based on the percentage distribution of the profile parameter value Pt . The new classification of erosion segments relies on the assumptions outlined in *Table 2*. From this perspective, it is possible to quantify individual erosion stages based on the above parameter, i.e., the total height of the profile (*Table 2*) or can be adapted to all erosion stages as indicated in *Figure 17*.

Table 2 New hierarchy of erosion activity from the perspective of time and spatial distribution of erosion stages

Aspect	Time Erosion (non-relativistic)	Spatial Erosion (relativistic)
Nature	Gradual with respect to time	Variable across area
Scale	Year, months, hours	Microscopic to macroscopic

Drivers	An incrementally increasing number of droplet impingements leads to damage accumulation within the impacted surface.	Uneven water velocity distribution, or deviation from the considered spherical droplet geometry, causes inhomogeneous impact conditions.
Material deformation	Incremental over time with variance in erosion rate, based on five erosion stages including incubation, acceleration maximum rate, deceleration, and terminal stages [51].	Different areas of the surface experience varying stages of erosion due to the non-uniform distribution of the droplets' velocity fields

This method, based on the total height of the profile, allows for the identification of individual areas irrespective of the duration of exposure before the onset of accelerated erosion (*Figure 17*) when material removal takes place. After material removal occurs, another type of parameter should be selected (i.e., depth), but the segmentation method could still be applied. From this viewpoint, it is evident that several erosion substages may exist between the pre-incubation phase and the acceleration phase. Their distribution is influenced by the physical structure and velocity characteristics of the water droplets [46]. This classification is based on the maximum **Pt** values according to the localized damage segment. This methodology also helps clarify that, for example, the effects of 60° and 75° are similar, with a slight advantage to 60°, which covers the area better. It may be because the inclination angle compensates for the uneven distribution of the drop velocity profile, resulting in a more symmetrical distribution of the **Pt** value (*Figure 15*) for angles 60° and 75°. The roughness at 45° decreases significantly, probably due to forcing the droplet into the shear, reducing its energy transfer into the material. Hattori and Kakuichi [22] similarly observed a drop in erosion rates (volume loss and mass loss) in the case of a 30° impact angle, compared to 90°, 60°, and 45° showing similar rates in the case of S15C steel using jet nozzle and flow rates of 180 m/s. These trends are similar to trends reported in this study where 75° and 60° impact angles show similar achieved erosion damage (in **Pt**, depth, and volume), but erosion caused by 45° impact angle drops considerably. It shows the possibility that there may be a critical angle based on impact speed, under which droplets are dominantly forced into shear.

Localized damage (*Table 2*) in water droplet erosion refers to a specific region on a surface where erosion is the most pronounced on the impacted surface due to the periodic or non-periodic impact of water droplets. The uneven erosion distribution across the impacted surface can be attributed to several factors. The angle at which droplets strike the surface influences significantly the erosion pattern. Typically, non-perpendicular impacts lead to uneven impact pressure distribution and localized damage [22]. Based on the results of the current study, using PWJ, perpendicular impact leads to significant erosion localization in a semicircular shape.

On the other hand, a 60° impact angle caused more evenly distributed erosion. The low damage segment shows significantly lower (<20 %) signs of erosion damage compared to the localized damage segment. In case of ideally circular droplet, low damage segment would copy the impact outer boundary. In the case observed in this experiment, it is a complementary area to the semicircular localized damage segment. The transitional segment connects localized damage segments and low-damage segments.

Uneven velocity [46] distribution across the droplet cross-section can result in different erosion stages occurring simultaneously within a single impact area, contributing to localized damage. Additionally, the size, speed, and frequency of the droplets can affect the erosion pattern, where larger or faster droplets cause more significantly localized damage. Studies using high-speed imaging and scanning

electron microscopy (SEM) have demonstrated that erosion is not uniformly distributed. Localized damage segments are often observed along the contact line where the impact pressure is highest [52].

The findings are built upon previous studies [7] and [53] in several ways. First, the results confirmed the transition momentum of roughness profile parameter P_t values. Second, the quantitative segmentation and classification of erosion stages, along with the innovative use of SEM and other measurement techniques, underscore the robustness and precision of the findings. It expanded the classification of erosion segment distribution using the total height of profile parameter along a new hierarchy of erosion activity from the point of view of time and spatial distribution of erosion stages for analyzing and estimating erosion patterns, contributing to more effective erosion management strategies using quantitative parameter P_t . Concerning the acceleration erosion stage and all further stages with prevalent material removal, similar approaches can be adapted for the segmentation of the crater using local depth evaluation (*Figure 17*).

Further studies should focus on optimizing the impact angles for various structural applications, similarly as in [54], particularly for complex-shaped surfaces like turbine blades [55]. Investigating a broader range of angles and their effects on erosion and surface roughening will help refine the understanding of optimal impact conditions and detailed characterization of materials, including grain structure and mechanical properties, to understand non-uniform erosion patterns and develop materials designed to withstand angled impingements. For the ongoing investigation, the factors contributing to uneven velocity field distribution across the droplet cross-section, including droplet generation techniques and flow dynamics, should be considered to achieve a more uniform impact pressure distribution.

Conclusions

The detailed analysis and experimental approach outlined in this study provide valuable insights into the complex interactions between water droplets and various surface angles at various erosion times. The following findings significantly enhance our understanding of erosion mechanisms, particularly in structural applications involving complex shapes. The findings indicate that exposure time and impact angle are critical factors in determining material removal and surface roughening. These insights have significant implications for engineering strategies, especially in applications involving water turbine blades and wind turbine blades, where the angle of incidence is rarely perpendicular to the surface. The findings challenge the traditional theory of water droplets acting as spherical objects in two-dimensional Euclidean space, offering a more detailed understanding of erosion behavior using quantitative parameter P_t . Considering both non-relativistic and relativistic perspectives, this research provides the following concluding remarks:

- Exposure longer than 3 s leads to material removal, while shorter exposure times result in surface roughening, which is relevant for wear resistance studies.
- Erosion development is not uniform, likely due to uneven velocity field distribution across the droplet cross-section or deviations of droplet geometry, leading to different erosion stages occurring simultaneously within a single cross-section.
- Segmentation of erosion damage helps predict material removal locations and quantify individual erosion stages influenced by droplet velocity characteristics.
- P_t values obtained for 60° and 75° show similar effects, with 60° slightly better coverage of the treated area. Roughness decreases significantly at 45°, likely due to the droplet partially experiencing shear, reducing its energy transfer into the material.

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Declaration of competing interest

The corresponding author declares on behalf of all the authors of a submission that they have no known competing financial interests, personal relationships, or potential conflicts of interest that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be available following publication at [10.5281/zenodo.15063706](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15063706)

Author contributions

Jakub Poloprudský: Conceptualization, Methodology, Resources, Writing – original draft, Data curation, Validation, Writing – review & editing; **Alice Chlupová:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing; **Štěpán Gamanov:** Investigation, Methodology, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing; **Dagmar Klichová:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Software; **Gabriel Stolárik:** Investigation, Methodology, Software; **Akash Nag:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Methodology, Validation, Writing – original draft; **Sergej Hloch:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing

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